

Impact of Urban Growth on Workforce Participation and Occupational Structure in Jaipur City (Rajasthan, India)

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Abstract This paper highlights the trends and patterns of urban growth and its impact on the workforce participation and occupational structure in the Jaipur city. The absolute growth of the urban population is continuously increasing and the annual growth rate of the urban population of the Rajasthan state is continuously decreasing. In the process of urbanization and economic development, Jaipur MC has emerged as a primate city. The results of the urban population growth show that at the state level the decadal population growth rate is declining continuously since 1981. In the Jaipur city the average exponential growth rate of the urban population is declining since 1991 but has increased slightly in the census year 2011. The built-up change and associated changes in the infrastructure and economic activities cause changes in the workforce participation occupational structure of the urban workers. The results show that the share of male urban workers was 85.77% in 2001 that decreased to 83.61% in 2011. In contrary the share of female urban workers was 14.23% in 2001 that increased to 16.39% in 2011.

Keywords Urban Growth, Exponential Growth, Workforce Participation, Occupational Structure, Jaipur

Introduction The nations of the world are interconnecting globally and currently, more than 50% of the world's population (54 percent) lives in urban areas (United Nations Prospects). It is estimated that by 2050, 75% population of the developing nations will be urban population (Montgomery, 2008). The urbanization and urban sprawl is accelerating at an alarming pace that is expected to pose serious challenges to urban planners and dwellers in developing nations (Sudhira et al, 2004; Oztruk, 2017). According to the United Nations report in India by 2045, 50 % population will be living in urban areas (United Nations population prospects 2018). Though the rapid economic growth is boosting urban development in India but India still lags behind other developing economies like Brazil, Mexico or even China, etc. (Chauvin et al. 2017). There are various methods for measuring and mapping urban landscape morphology and urban sprawl. The list includes Shannon's entropy, fractal analysis, shape index, contagion index, and Moran's I (Bhatta 2012; Munafu and Congedo 2013; Zeng et al. 2014). In urban studies, the built-up assessment is considered as a parameter of urban sprawl (Torrens and Alberti, 2000; Barnes et al., 2001; Epstein et al., 2002, Sudhira et al. 2004; Bhat et al. 2017). The latest studies suggest that the integration of remote sensing techniques and geographical information systems has been quite effective in measuring and modelling urban growth and sprawl. These are the refined monitoring systems that are more reliable and successful when it is combined with ancillary information (Jat et al, 2008; Sudhira et al, 2003). The main objective of this paper is to analyse the urban growth of Jaipur city from 2000 to 2010 and 2019.

Aim of study This paper outlines a macro-level analysis of trends and patterns of urban growth and its impact on the workforce participation and occupational structure in the Jaipur city of Rajasthan state.

Review of Literature Rajasthan state shares 10.4% geographical area of India. As per census 2011, the total population of Rajasthan is 68548437, out of which 24.87% is urban population and 75.13% is rural population. In census 2011 it was observed that at the national level it was the first census decade in which absolute growth in urban population was higher than the absolute growth in rural population. This is a clear indication that the rapid growth of the urban population and increasing size and

number of urban areas will significantly transform the land use and economic structure of the urban periphery. The total number of towns in India in 2001 was 5161 which increased to 7934 in 2011. The total population of Rajasthan has increased from 56.5 million (2001) to 68.5 million (2011). In 1901, only 14% population was living in urban areas. According to the census 2011, the urban population of Rajasthan is 17.04 million that is 24.87% of the total population. In Rajasthan, the urbanization level is still lower than the national average. Out of the 33 districts in the state, only the five major districts of Ajmer, Bikaner, Kota, Jaipur, and Jodhpur have a level of urbanisation that is higher than the national average (census 2011). Rest all other 28 districts have urbanization levels below the national average.

Main Text

Materials and Methods

1. Datasets

The census of India provides datasets on a decadal interval. In this chapter, primarily census datasets have been used to analyse the pattern and growth of Jaipur Municipal Corporation (JMC) in Rajasthan. The latest datasets used in the study are from the Census-2011. The following census tables, Primary Census Abstracts (PCA) and Town Directories (TD) from the various census years have been used for the analysis.

1. *Provisional population totals, Paper-2, volume-1, rural-urban distribution India, series-1, Census of India, 2011.*
2. *Primary Census Abstract (PCA) Rajasthan (total table), Census 1991, 2002 and 2011.*
3. *Primary Census Abstract (PCA) Jaipur district, Census 1991, 2002 and 2011.*
4. *Town directory, Rajasthan, Census of India, 2001.*
5. *Town directory, Rajasthan, Census of India, 2011.*

2. Methods

Decadal urban population growth rate shows % change in the urban population of an area during a decade. It has been calculated from 1901 to 2011 using following equation.

$$\%R_{di} = \left[\frac{\{Pop_i(\text{current census year}) - Pop_i(\text{previous census year})\}}{Pop_i(\text{previous census year})} \right] \times 100 \quad (4.8)$$

Where, '% R_{di} ' is the decadal urban population growth rate of ' i^{th} ' region and ' Pop_i ' is the population of ' i^{th} ' region in a particular census year.

The average annual exponential growth rate reveals the annual change in urban population during particular census duration. It has been calculated using the following equation.

$$\%R_{ai} = (100/t) \left\{ \log_e \left(\frac{P_1}{P_0} \right) \right\} \quad (4.9)$$

Where, '% R_{ai} ' is the annual exponential growth rate (%) for ' i^{th} ' region, ' P_1 ' is the population in current census year, ' P_0 ' is the population in previous census year and ' t ' is the duration between two census years.

Main Text

As per the Census of India 2011, at the national level, the level of urbanization increased from 27.7% in 2001 to 31.17% in 2011 with a growth rate of 2.76% per annum during 2001-2011. For the first time, it was observed that the absolute growth in the urban population has outnumbered the absolute growth in the rural population (Census 2011). The state-wise analysis of the percentage urban population shows that in 2011, Rajasthan state stands 27th among 35 states and union territories of India. In terms of percentage urban population, Rajasthan state still lags far behind union territories, national average (i.e. 31.16%), and other

states of India (Census 2011). In the last census decade, the maximum absolute urban population has been added as compared to other census decades.

The economic growth and developmental activities are encouraging growth in the number and size of census towns in Rajasthan but the process of urbanization is slower than in other states of India. The 24.87% urban population of Rajasthan is living in 297 towns, out of which 185 are statutory towns and 112 are census towns. In Rajasthan, the size class-wise population distribution shows that more than half of the urban population is living in class-I towns. In the state, the population distribution of class-I towns is concordant with the rank-size rule distribution.

Result and Discussion

1. Pattern of urban growth in the Jaipur Municipal Corporation

In 2001 and 2011 the decadal urban population growth rate was 31.26% and 29.01% respectively. The decadal urban population growth rate of Rajasthan state was highest at 58.69% in 1981, after that it is continuously decreasing. In the last three census decades, the urban population growth rate is not only below the national average but also declining continuously. The average annual exponential growth rate of the urban population of Rajasthan was the highest (4.62%) in 1981. Table 2 gives the picture that from 1901 to 2011 the average annual exponential population growth rate was lower in Rajasthan (2.40% per annum) than the national average (2.68% per annum). According to the census 2011, the average annual exponential growth rate of the urban population of Rajasthan state was 2.55%, i.e. lower than the national average (2.76%). Table 2 highlights that in Rajasthan the average annual exponential growth rate of the urban population is continuously decreasing since 1981.

Table 1: Decadal urban population growth rate (1901-2011).

Census decade	India	Rajasthan	Jaipur (M Corp.)
1901-11	0.36	-4.83	-14.40
1911-21	8.26	-0.03	-12.32
1921-31	19.12	17.21	19.94
1931-41	31.98	22.43	21.94
1941-51	41.40	39.59	65.59
1951-61	26.41	11.04	38.58
1961-71	38.23	38.47	52.50
1971-81	46.14	58.69	58.82
1981-91	36.44	39.62	49.26
1991-01	31.51	31.26	59.25
2001-11	31.80	29.01	31.15

Rajasthan state covers 10.4% area of the country, but there are only 3 million-plus cities out of 53 million-plus cities of India (Census, 2011). According to the census 2001, Jaipur MC was the only million-plus city in Rajasthan. As per the census 2011, there are 3 million-plus cities in Rajasthan i.e. Jaipur MC, Jodhpur MC, and Kota MC with a population of 3046163, 1056191, and 1001694 respectively. Table 1 shows that in 2011 the decadal urban population growth rate of Jaipur MC was 31.15%, that was higher than the Rajasthan state average (i.e. 29.01%) and the national average (i.e. 31.8%).

Figure 1: Decadal population growth rate (1901-2011).

Table 2: Average annual exponential population growth rate (1901-2011).

Census decade	India	Rajasthan	Jaipur (M Corp.)
1901-11	0.04	-0.49	-1.56
1911-21	0.79	-0.00	-1.31
1921-31	1.75	1.59	1.82
1931-41	2.77	2.02	1.98
1941-51	3.46	3.34	5.04
1951-61	2.34	1.05	3.26
1961-71	3.24	3.25	4.22
1971-81	3.79	4.62	4.63
1981-91	3.11	3.34	4.00
1991-01	2.74	2.72	4.65
2001-11	2.76	2.55	2.71
1901-2011	2.68	2.40	2.95

Table 2 shows that from 1901-2011 the average annual exponential population growth rate was 2.95% in Jaipur MC that was higher than the state and national average. From 1991-2011, out of the three million-plus cities of Rajasthan, only Kota MC and Jaipur MC shows a higher average annual exponential growth rate of urban population than the national average. During 2001-2011 the average annual exponential growth rate of the urban population was measured 2.71% in Jaipur MC. During 1961-2001 the average annual exponential growth rate of Jaipur MC has always been higher than 4%. In 2001 and 2011 the average annual exponential growth rate of Jaipur MC was 4.65% and 2.71% respectively.

Figure 2: Average annual exponential population growth rate (1901-2011).

2. Change in the workforce participation and occupational structure

Table 3 gives the distribution of workforce participation and occupational structure of the urban population in the Jaipur city of Rajasthan state for the census years 2001 and 2011. Out of the total urban workers, the share of male urban workers was 85.77% in 2001 that decreased to 83.61% in 2011. The share of female urban workers was 14.23% in 2001 that increased to 16.39% in 2011. It is a good indicator of the women empowerment as the share of female urban workers is increasing in total urban workers of the Jaipur MC. In 2001 there are 92.7% total main urban workers and 7.3% are total marginal urban workers in the Jaipur MC. In 2011 there are 93.29% total main urban workers and 6.71% total marginal urban workers. Table 3 shows that the share of total main urban workers has increased while share of total marginal urban workers has decreased in the census year 2011. One interesting outcome is that the share of female main urban workers has increased from 11.55% in 2001 to 13.74% in 2011.

Table 3: Workforce participation and occupational structure of urban workers of Jaipur Municipal Corporation.

Urban workers	Sex	JAIPUR	
		2001	2011
% Main workers	Male	81.15	79.56
	Female	11.55	13.74
	Total	92.7	93.29
% Marginal workers	Male	4.63	4.05
	Female	2.67	2.65
	Total	7.3	6.71
% Cultivators	Male	1.49	1.28
	Female	1.21	0.72
	Total	2.7	2.01

% Agricultural labourers	Male	0.36	0.73
	Female	0.35	0.3
	Total	0.71	1.03
% Household workers	Male	4.08	4.06
	Female	1.44	1.27
	Total	5.51	5.33
% Other workers	Male	79.85	77.54
	Female	11.23	14.1
	Total	91.08	91.63
% Total workers	Male	85.77	83.61
	Female	14.23	16.39
	Total	100	100

The share of total urban cultivators to total urban workers has decreased from 2.7% in 2001 to 2.01% in 2011. The share of both male and female urban cultivators to total urban workers has decreased from 2001 to 2011. The share of total urban agricultural labourers to total urban workers has increased from 0.71% in 2001 to 1.03% in 2011. The share of male urban agricultural labourers has increased while the share of female urban agricultural labourers has decreased from 2001 to 2011. The share of total urban household workers to total urban workers has decreased from 5.51% in 2001 to 5.33% in 2011. The share of both male and female urban household workers to total urban workers has decreased from 2001 to 2011. The share of total urban other workers to total urban workers has increased marginally from 91.08% in 2001 to 91.63% in 2011. It is interesting to see that share of male other urban workers to total workers has decreased from 79.85% in 2001 to 77.54% in 2011 while the share of female other urban workers has increased significantly from 11.23% in 2001 to 14.10% in 2011. It can be summarized that the share of main urban workers to total urban workers is increasing. As well as in all occupations the share of female urban workers to total urban workers is also increasing significantly.

Conclusion It is clear from the results that in the last 2 census decades Jaipur city is experiencing higher rate of urban growth than the state and national average. In 2011 the decadal growth rate of the state was 29.01% and the annual exponential growth rate was 2.55%. During 1901-2011 the annual growth of the urban population of Rajasthan has remained below the national average. The trend of annual exponential growth rate shows that in recent decades Jaipur MC is growing faster positively. The built-up change and associated changes in the infrastructure and economic activities cause changes in the workforce participation occupational structure of the urban workers. The share of female urban workers has increased in all sectors of occupation in the Jaipur city. An interesting finding is that the share of total urban cultivators and female urban cultivators has decreased in Jaipur MC, while the share of urban agricultural labourers has increased in all million-plus cities of Rajasthan. During 2001-2011 the share of other urban workers has increased in Jaipur MC. Overall it is observed that Jaipur MC is the largest and fastest sprawling urban centre of Rajasthan

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